

Synthesis and characterization of nitrosylpseudochromium(I) complexes with morpholinomethyl urea and related ligands

Ekta, S. Raina, M. S. Pathania, H. N. Sheikh* and B. L. Kalsotra

Department of Chemistry, University of Jammu, Jammu-180 006, Jammu & Kashmir, India

E-mail : hnsheikh@rediffmail.com

Manuscript received 21 August 2006, revised 15 June 2007, accepted 18 June 2007

Abstract : Synthesis and characterization of nitrosylpseudochromium(I) complexes of the composition, $[\text{Cr}(\text{NO})\text{X}_2\text{L}.\text{H}_2\text{O}]$, where $\text{X} = \text{NCS}^-$ or NCO^- and $\text{L} =$ morpholinomethyl urea (MMU), morpholinomethyl thiourea (MMTU), piperidinomethyl urea (PMU) or piperidinomethyl thiourea (PMTU) is presented. These complexes have been prepared by treatment of potassium chromate with potassium thiocyanate/potassium cyanate and hydroxylamine hydrochloride followed by the addition of ligand (L). The complexes have been characterized by usual procedure.

Keywords : Chromium(I) complexes, nitrosyl complexes, mixed ligand complexes.

Extensive studies have been made on the synthesis and stereochemistry of chromium nitrosyl complexes¹. Reaction of pentacyanonitrosylchromate(I) with nitrogen donor ligands like 2,2'-bipyridyl (bipy), 1,10-phenanthroline (*o*-phen), pyridine (Py) and quinoline (Qu) lead to formation of complexes of the type, $[\text{Cr}(\text{NO})(\text{CN})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{L}_2]$, where $\text{L} = \text{Py}$ or Qu and $[\text{Cr}(\text{NO})(\text{CN})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})\text{L}]$, where $\text{L} = \text{bipy}$ or *o*-phen². A large number of mixed ligand complexes of metal nitrosyl complexes have been synthesized and characterized by various workers³.

The present paper describes the synthesis and characterization of mixed ligand complexes of nitrosylpseudochromium(I) having general formula, $[\text{Cr}(\text{NO})\text{X}_2\text{L}.\text{H}_2\text{O}]$, where $\text{X} = \text{NCS}^-$ or NCO^- and $\text{L} = \text{MMU}$, MMTU , PMU or PMTU .

Results and discussion

Tables 1 and 2 give the analytical and spectral data of the complexes. All the complexes are mononuclear with general formula, $[\text{Cr}(\text{NO})\text{X}_2\text{L}.\text{H}_2\text{O}]$, where $\text{X} = \text{NCS}^-$ or NCO^- and $\text{L} = \text{MMU}$, MMTU , PMU or PMTU . These complexes are coloured solids, stable in air at room temperature. They are insoluble in water, partially soluble in ethanol, DMF, DMSO and other organic solvents and soluble in glacial acetic acid. All these complexes decompose above 260 °C.

The molar conductance values of all the complexes in glacial acetic acid are in the range 9.68–19.36 $\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$ which indicate non-electrolytic nature of the com-

plexes (Table 1). Magnetic moments of the complexes are in the range 1.77–1.86 B.M. indicating the presence of one unpaired electron as expected for low spin chromium(I) complexes (Table 1). Similar results have been reported by various workers for nitrosylchromium(I) complexes⁴.

All complexes (1-8) show a sharp absorption band in the range 1700–1745 cm^{-1} which can be assigned to stretching mode $\nu(\text{NO})$ of linearly bonded MNO group. Appearance of weak band at 620–640 cm^{-1} may be attributed to $\nu(\text{Cr}-\text{NO})$ ⁵.

Strong and wide bands in the range 3400–3550 cm^{-1} can be attributed to stretching modes $\nu_s(\text{OH})$ and $\nu_a(\text{OH})$ of coordinated water molecule. Sharp absorption band which lies in the range 1600–1630 cm^{-1} can be attributed to bending mode of coordinated water. In addition to these fundamental modes, complexes also exhibit additional mode in the region 800–900 cm^{-1} which can be assigned to rocking modes of coordinated water molecule⁶.

A single sharp and highly intense band was seen in the range 2085–2096 cm^{-1} (complexes 1-4) which corresponds to stretching modes of $\nu(\text{CN})$ of thiocyanate group. A weak band in the range 839–845 cm^{-1} due to $\nu(\text{CS})$ stretching vibration exhibits a significant positive shift in complexes as compared to free thiocyanate group. Both these observations are indicative of N-bonded thiocyanate group in complexes. A sharp band appears in the region 2170–2210 cm^{-1} (complexes 5-8) corresponding to $\nu(\text{CN})$ stretching mode of (CNO) which indicates a

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of complexes

Sl. no.	Complexes (Emp. formula)	Colour	Analysis (%) : Found (Calcd.)					Molar conductivity ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	Magnetic moment μ_{eff} (B.M)
			Cr	C	H	N	S		
1.	(1) $[\text{Cr}(\text{NO})(\text{NCS})_2 \cdot \text{MMU} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$ ($\text{CrC}_8\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_6\text{O}_4\text{S}_2$)	Green	13.84 (13.85)	25.57 (25.59)	4.00 (4.03)	22.30 (22.39)	17.01 (17.08)	9.68	1.79
2.	(2) $[\text{Cr}(\text{NO})(\text{NCS})_2 \cdot \text{MMTU} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$ ($\text{CrC}_8\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_6\text{O}_3\text{S}_3$)	Green	13.20 (13.28)	24.50 (24.55)	3.85 (3.86)	21.41 (21.47)	24.55 (24.57)	9.63	1.82
3.	(3) $[\text{Cr}(\text{NO})(\text{NCS})_2 \cdot \text{PMU} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$ ($\text{CrC}_9\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_6\text{O}_3$)	Light green	13.89 (13.92)	28.97 (28.95)	4.57 (4.50)	22.49 (22.51)	17.16 (17.17)	19.36	1.78
4.	(4) $[\text{Cr}(\text{NO})(\text{NCS})_2 \cdot \text{PMTU} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$ ($\text{CrC}_9\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_6\text{O}_2\text{S}$)	Dark green	13.33 (13.35)	27.74 (27.75)	4.31 (4.39)	21.56 (21.58)	24.59 (24.69)	19.36	1.81
5.	(5) $[\text{Cr}(\text{NO})(\text{NCO})_2 \cdot \text{MMU} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$ ($\text{CrC}_8\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_6\text{O}_6$)	Green	15.17 (15.15)	27.93 (27.99)	4.39 (4.40)	24.47 (24.48)	-	9.68	1.77
6.	(6) $[\text{Cr}(\text{NO})(\text{NCO})_2 \cdot \text{MMTU} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$ ($\text{CrC}_8\text{H}_{15}\text{N}_6\text{O}_5\text{S}$)	Blackish green	14.48 (14.47)	26.71 (26.74)	4.22 (4.21)	23.40 (23.39)	8.90 (8.92)	19.36	1.85
7.	(7) $[\text{Cr}(\text{NO})(\text{NCO})_2 \cdot \text{PMU} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$ ($\text{CrC}_9\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_6\text{O}_5$)	Green	15.20 (15.24)	31.69 (31.67)	5.05 (5.02)	24.61 (24.63)	-	9.68	1.86
8.	(8) $[\text{Cr}(\text{NO})(\text{NCO})_2 \cdot \text{PMTU} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$ ($\text{CrC}_9\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_6\text{O}_4\text{S}$)	Blackish green	14.53 (14.55)	30.20 (30.25)	4.80 (4.79)	23.49 (23.52)	8.95 (8.97)	19.36	1.82

Table 2. Electronic spectral data of the complexes

Sl. no.	Complex	ν_1 (nm) ϵ ($\text{L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$)	ν_2 (nm) ϵ ($\text{L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$)	ν_3 (nm) ϵ ($\text{L mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$)
		${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2A_1$	${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_1$	${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2E$
1.	$[\text{Cr}(\text{NO})(\text{NCS})_2 \cdot \text{MMU} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$	655 (65)	425 (95)	260 (3500)
2.	$[\text{Cr}(\text{NO})(\text{NCS})_2 \cdot \text{MMTU} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$	660 (70)	430 (85)	262 (3000)
3.	$[\text{Cr}(\text{NO})(\text{NCS})_2 \cdot \text{PMU} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$	666 (55)	435 (90)	260 (3300)
4.	$[\text{Cr}(\text{NO})(\text{NCS})_2 \cdot \text{PMTU} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$	658 (80)	432 (85)	265 (3700)
5.	$[\text{Cr}(\text{NO})(\text{NCO})_2 \cdot \text{MMU} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$	659 (75)	438 (75)	262 (2800)
6.	$[\text{Cr}(\text{NO})(\text{NCO})_2 \cdot \text{MMTU} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$	662 (70)	435 (65)	263 (2200)
7.	$[\text{Cr}(\text{NO})(\text{NCO})_2 \cdot \text{PMU} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$	668 (65)	428 (90)	262 (2500)
8.	$[\text{Cr}(\text{NO})(\text{NCO})_2 \cdot \text{PMTU} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$	670 (70)	423 (95)	264 (2500)

positive shift from that of free CNO (2160 cm^{-1}). The $\nu(\text{CNO})$ symmetric stretching mode which appears in the range $1320\text{--}1350 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, indicates a positive shift from free cyanate group (1282 cm^{-1}). These bands are indicative of nitrogen bonded cyanato group⁷.

In complexes (1, 3, 5 and 7), $[\text{Cr}(\text{NO})\text{X}_2\text{L} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$, where L = MMU or PMU, $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ mode of MMU is lowered by 30 cm^{-1} due to Cr–O bonding and draining of electron density from carbonyl group of MMU to chromium. The $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ stretching mode in MMU and PMU ligand appears at 1655 and 1660 cm^{-1} respectively. Moreover, $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N}-\text{C})$ stretching modes of morpholine and piperidine rings of MMU and PMU are shifted to lower frequencies by about 40 cm^{-1} due to involvement of ring nitrogen of morpholine and piperidine in formation of

coordinate bond with chromium. The $\nu(\text{C}-\text{N}-\text{C})$, stretching modes in free MMU and PMU ligand appears at 1165 , 1140 cm^{-1} and 1150 , 1120 cm^{-1} respectively. Negative shifts in $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ and $\nu(\text{C}-\text{N}-\text{C})$ stretching modes of MMU and PMU in complexes indicates bidentate modes of bonding of these ligands in complexes. A slight positive shift in C–O–C stretching vibration of morpholine ring in complexes indicates that morpholine does not involve its oxygen in bond formation.

In complexes (2, 4, 6 and 8), $[\text{Cr}(\text{NO})\text{X}_2\text{L} \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$, where L = MMTU or PMTU, there is a negative shift in stretching frequencies of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ by 20 to 25 cm^{-1} due to drainage of electron density from C=S to metal chromium on complexation of ligand to chromium. The $\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$ stretching modes in free MMTU and PMTU appears at 1295 ,

1310 cm^{-1} . Also, (C-N-C) stretching mode of morpholine and piperidine rings of MMTU and PMTU appear at lower frequencies as sharp bands than in free ligands in which bands appears at 1165, 1130 cm^{-1} and at 1160, 1120 cm^{-1} respectively.

These observations indicate that ligands behave in bidentate fashion in complexes.

Electronic spectra of chromium(I) complexes have been extensively studied and tentative assignments of bands have been made (Table 2). In the complexes of chromium(I) of the type $[\text{Cr}(\text{NO})\text{L}_5]^{n-}$, where $\text{L} = \text{CN}$ or NH_3 , an important interaction between d_{xz} , d_{yz} , orbitals of chromium and $p\pi$ orbitals of the nitrosyl group assumed to be NO^+ have been observed⁸. Magnetic susceptibility and electron spin resonance studies have confirmed that the complexes of the type $[\text{CrX}_2\text{NOL}]$, where $\text{L} =$ bidentate ligand and $\text{X} = \text{CN}^-$ and CNS^- are low spin complexes containing unpaired electron in d_{xy} (b_2) orbital^{9,10}.

In the complexes of the type, $[\text{Cr}(\text{NO})(\text{NCS})_2\text{L}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ and $[\text{Cr}(\text{NO})(\text{NCO})_2\text{L}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$, where $\text{L} = \text{MMU}$, MMTU, PMU or PMTU three bands were recorded in the range 200–800 nm (Table 2). These three bands suggest a distorted octahedral arrangement of ligands around chromium containing five electrons in $e^4b_2^1$ configuration. First band appears as broad and weak band in the region 655–670 nm which can be assigned to $b_2(d_{xy}) - a_1(d_{z^2})$ transition. Second band appears as weak and broad band in the range 420–440 nm and can be assigned to $b_2(d_{xy}) \rightarrow b_1(d_{x^2-y^2})$ transition. Third band appears as highly intense and sharp band in the range 260–270 nm and can be assigned to $b_2(d_{xy}) \rightarrow e(\pi^*\cdot\text{NO}^+)$ transition. Second band can be assigned as equal to 10 Dq value of the complexes.

Thermal studies : The TG curve of two representative complexes **1** and **5** were recorded in the temperature range of 35–850 $^\circ\text{C}$.

The decomposition of the complex, $[\text{Cr}(\text{NO})(\text{NCS})_2\text{MMU}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ is completed in three steps which is supported by three endothermic peaks in DTA curve (Fig. 1). The complex shows an initial weight loss of 4.85% around the temperature of 150 $^\circ\text{C}$ corresponding to the loss of one water molecule (calculated 4.79%). A further weight loss of 42.68% around the temperature of 400 $^\circ\text{C}$ corresponds to the loss of ligand MMU (calculated 42.40%). Thereafter, a continuous weight loss of 8.0% is observed around a temperature of 750 $^\circ\text{C}$ correspond-

Fig. 1. TGA/DTA studies of $[\text{Cr}(\text{NO})(\text{NCS})_2\text{MMU}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$.

ing to loss of one NO molecule (calculated 7.99%). Thereafter no further weight loss is observed probably due to the formation of stable $[\text{Cr}(\text{NCS})_2]$.

Similarly the decomposition of the complex, $[\text{Cr}(\text{NO})(\text{NCO})_2\text{MMU}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ is completed in three steps which is supported by three endothermic peaks in DTA curve (Fig. 2). The complex shows an initial weight loss of 5.33% around the temperature of 150 $^\circ\text{C}$ corresponding to the loss of one water molecule (calculated 5.24%). A further weight loss of 46.13% around the temperature

Fig. 2. TGA/DTA studies of $[\text{Cr}(\text{NO})(\text{NCO})_2\text{MMU}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$.

of 400 $^\circ\text{C}$ corresponds to the loss of ligand MMU (calculated 46.37%). Thereafter, a continuous weight loss of 8.81% is observed around a temperature of 750 $^\circ\text{C}$ corresponding to loss of one NO molecule (calculated 8.74%). Thereafter no further weight loss is observed probably due to the formation of stable $[\text{Cr}(\text{NCO})_2]$.

Based on the above observation the following tentative structure is assigned to the complexes $[\text{Cr}(\text{NO})\text{X}_2\text{L}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$, where $\text{X} = \text{NCS}^-$ or NCO^- and $\text{L} = \text{MMU}$, MMTU, PMU or PMTU.

Experimental

Morpholine (Fluka A.G.), b.p. 120.3 °C and piperidine (SDS), b.p. 106 °C were purified by distillation after keeping these bases over KOH pellets over night. Urea (Merck), m.p. 132–134 °C, thiourea (Ranbaxy), m.p. 175–177 °C, formaldehyde (Qualigens), potassium chromate (SDS), m.p. 968.3 °C, phosphorous pentachloride (SDS), glacial acetic acid (SDS), b.p. 117.9 °C were used as supplied. Carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen and sulphur were analysed microanalytically using CHNS analyzer Leco make model-932. Chromium was estimated gravimetrically by reported method¹¹. Sulphur was estimated gravimetrically as barium sulphate¹¹. Molar conductivity in DMF at room temperature was measured by Elico conductivity bridge type CM82T having conductivity cell with a cell constant of 0.74 using 10^{-3} M solution of complexes. IR spectra of complexes over the region 4000–400 cm^{-1} were recorded on FTIR spectrophotometer, Perkin-Elmer make, using KBr disc. Electronic spectra were run in DMF on Beckman DU-6 spectrophotometer in the 190–800 nm range using 10^{-3} M solution of the complexes. Magnetic measurements at room temperature were carried out by Gouy's method. TGA/DTG studies have been carried out using Perkin-Elmer (Pyris Diamond) thermal analyser in N_2 atmosphere in the temperature range of 100–1000 °C at a heating rate 10° per minute. The ligands were prepared by reported method.

Preparation of complexes :

$[\text{Cr}(\text{NO})(\text{NCS})_2\text{L}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ (where L = MMU, MMTU, PMU or PMTU) :

Potassium chromate (0.005 mol, 0.97 g) was dissolved in 30 ml of water. To this was added potassium thiocyanate (0.04 mol, 3.8 g) and hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.015 mol, 1.04 g) with constant stirring followed by addition of ligand, L 0.005 mol, (MMU = 0.79 g, MMTU = 0.87 g, PMU = 0.79 g and PMTU = 0.86 g) in 10 ml of water. The reaction mixture was refluxed for one hour when coloured precipitates appeared. The complexes so

formed were filtered, washed with water and ethanol 2 to 3 times and dried in vacuum desiccator. The analytical data of the complexes corresponded to the formula, $[\text{Cr}(\text{NO})(\text{NCS})_2\text{L}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$, where L = MMU, MMTU, PMU or PMTU.

$[\text{Cr}(\text{NO})(\text{NCO})_2\text{L}\cdot\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ (where L = MMU, MMTU, PMU or PMTU) :

Potassium chromate (0.005 mol, 0.97 g) was dissolved in 30 ml of distilled water. To this was added potassium cyanate (0.04 mol, 3.2 g) and hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.015 mol, 1.04 g) with constant stirring followed by addition of ligand, L 0.005 mol, (MMU = 0.76 g, MMTU = 0.87 g, PMU = 0.79 g and PMTU = 0.86 g) in 10 ml of water. The reaction mixture was refluxed for one hour when coloured precipitates appeared. The complexes so formed were filtered, washed with water and ethanol and dried in vacuum desiccator.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (M.S.P.) is thankful to U.G.C., New Delhi for the award of teacher fellowship under FIP Scheme.

References

1. R. C. Maurya, D. C. Gupta, R. K. Shukla, N. Anandam and M. R. Maurya, *Transition Met. Chem.*, 1987, **12**, 273; R. C. Maurya, R. K. Shukla and D. C. Gupta, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1987, **17**, 333.
2. R. C. Maurya, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1983, **22**, 529.
3. R. C. Maurya, S. Jaiswal and R. Verma, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1996, **35**, 998; R. C. Maurya, S. K. Jhakar and S. Batalia, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2000, **39**, 867; R. C. Maurya, S. Pillai, T. Singh, H. Singh and R. Shukla, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1998, **28**, 1103; R. G. Bhattacharya, G. P. Bhattacharyjee and N. Ghosh, *Polyhedron*, 1983, **2**, 543; R. C. Maurya and R. Verma, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1997, **37**, 147; R. C. Maurya, D. D. Mishra, S. K. Jaiswal and J. Dubey, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1995, **25**, 521; R. C. Maurya, H. Singh, J. Dubey and G. P. Shukla, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1997, **27**, 647; R. C. Maurya, J. Dubey and B. Shukla, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 1998, **28**, 1159; A. Sabstiyani and D. Venkappaya, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1984, **61**, 16; H. N. Sheikh, B. L. Kalsotra and Khema Shree, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2003, **80**, 909; M. S. Pathania, A. Hussain, H. N. Sheikh and B. L. Kalsotra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **82**, 594; Ashaq Hussain, H. N. Sheikh and B. L. Kalsotra, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2006, **83**, 531.
4. I. S. Ahuja and R. Sriramulu, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1980, **19**, 189.
5. I. Nakagawa and T. Shimanouchi, *Spectrochem. Acta*, 1964, **20**, 429.

Ekta *et al.* : Synthesis and characterization of nitrosylpseudohalochromium(I) complexes *etc.*

6. A. Sabatini and I. Bertini, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 989.
7. S. J. Patel and D. G. Tuck, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1968, 1970; H. Kobayashi, I. Trujikawa, M. Mori and Y. Yamamoto, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1969, **42**, 709.
8. A. B. P. Lever, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", 2nd ed., Elsevier, 1984; A. Keller and B. Jezowska-Trzebiatsowska, *Polyhedron*, 1985, **4**, 1847.
9. R. C. Maurya, A. Pandey and R. Verma, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 2002, **41**, 339.
10. R. C. Maurya and R. Verma, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1997, **36**, 437.
11. J. Bassett, R. C. Denney, G. H. Jeffery and J. Mendham, "Vogel's Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 4th ed., 1978, p. 859.